

**EXPERIENCE OF CREATION OF THE MODERN ANALYSERS OF
NATURAL AND ARTIFICIAL MAGNETIC MIKRO FIELDS: NEW
INSTRUMENTS FOR MEDICAL-BIOLOGICAL AND ECOLOGICAL
RESEARCHES**

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Numerous last year publications illuminating results experimental and clinical examinations of the biologic action of magnetic field (MF) on organs and system alive organism, bears evidence about sensitivity to the exposures of MF practically all main physiological systems which ensure optimum his workings and interactions with surrounding environment. Knownly, what MF can affect on organism how at the level of the physico-chemical conditions of ferment reactions proceed in cells, so and be stress mechanism acting on organism regulatore systems [1]. With the appearance of results, indicative of the MF influence on the health of man, does not uiet down dispute about the authenticity of their reception. Main motive for such distrusts is not so much absence distinct insight into the mechanism of MF action, as how many that, what in majority its explorers used enough the uncoordinated indices of the value of it exposition. Namely was absent how common approach in the application of the exposure doses of MF influence at the arranging of experiments, so and necessary for the arranging of these experiments of the remedy of measurements and MF monitoring. With the appearance of modern instruments allowing with high accuracy to control the MF recreation process and it parameters at the putting into effect of magnetobiologocal researches and to conduct the electromagnetic control of surrounding environment in premises, emerged real possibility to the systematization of carried out researches, to the decision of questions reproduce and rate setting of MF influence on man. The development of

modern domestic technology and the means of connection, when the real place of the arranging of researches can undergo influence of the several various kinds of MF sources and radiations, sets the questions of the creation of all-purpose means of their detection and instrumental control allowing to fix of MF spectral characteristics and its gradient, in the place of the experiment arranging. By means of MF spectrum analysers appear a good possibility to control MF amplitude and change in the wide frequencies range, to define the influence levels of each concrete source of radiation and hindrances to experiment.

During last year in IZMIRAN in this direction are conducted works as to the creation of new instruments which alongside with high technical characteristics must possess such all necessary parameters how: by comfort application in field and laboratory conditions, by reliability, by simplicity in using and by low cost [2, 3]. By active thrusts to idea creations and to building of magnetic spectrum analyzers are served not only stormy development computers and office technicians on workstation, but also carrying out researches about influence of natural MF on man's organism with the application of "doctor R.Voll methods" and instruments. To present time is created several new models of magnetometers allowing to conduct measurement constant and variable MF (including simultaneously), to conduct their spectral analysis. In their composition enter magnetometers of the MAGIC serieses (MF-01M, MF-03G, MF-06, MH-06M, MAF-08) and the digital systems of data logging of the IMPEDANCE serieses (IDL-04M, IDL-07, IDL-07M, IDL-08, IDL-10) built on induction, fluxgate and Hall MF sensors, the experience of creation and applications which, of main their dignity and characteristics are discussed in report.

1. Gitchev Yu.P., Gitchev Yu.Yu. Alleged health effects of electromagnetic fields. Novosibirsk, 1999.- 91 p.

2. Lyubimov V. V. Artificial and natural EMF in surrounding man environment and instruments for their revelation and fixation. Preprint of IZMIRAN No. 11 (1127) Troitsk, 1999. - 28 p.
3. Lyubimov V. V. Instruments of "IMPEDANCE" for geophysics and medicine// Pribory and Technika Experimenta. M.: Science, 2000. No.2. P. 157-158.